

Review Article

Strategies for Motivating Lecturers/Instructors toward High Productivity
for the Realization of Forestry Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Forestry education has great importance in development of any country. But, unfortunately, its benefit is yet to be recognized properly in Nigeria. For over a decade, countries have been working to uplift their educational standard by providing quality higher education to their citizens, which is resulted into the formulation of various educational policies, apart from the fact that Lecturers/Instructors are regarded as the key players in the forest education. However, they are often accused of low performance and blamed for failing standard in Forestry education because of poor attitude to duty by some of them. This negativity has been attributed to various factors particularly insufficient motivation. The government and stakeholders in forest education have recently been taking giant strides towards restructuring and repositioning our forest educational system through various reforms. This paper examined other practical strategies, which could be adopted to spur Lecturer/Instructors toward high productivity for the actualizing of the objectives of forestry education for national development.

Keywords: Forestry Education, Lecturers/Instructors, Nigeria.

Received: 10 March 2019

Accepted: 08 June 2019

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ISSN: 2141 – 4181

Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

“To educate means to suggest a proposal, but the proposal must be in response to a lived question or else it will simply be a load dumped on the one’s shoulder” (Guissain, 1995). While forestry education is a process (impacting and acquiring knowledge for understanding of an environment and used for good of self and general society (Adekola *et al.*, 2007).

The above quotation Guissain (1995) and Adekola *et al.* (2007) clearly expresses the increasing dysfunctionality in contemporary Nigerian forestry education. Both educationalists and non-educationists have since come to the conclusion that forestry education, system requires continuous upgrading and standardization so as to addressing the relevant issues of our national life. It has thus become imperative that the system needs to be repositioned to deal with the realities that so glaringly stare us in the face. The major aim of this paper is to present strategic ways of enhancing effective forestry lecturers and technologists toward high productivity and resources utilization in Nigeria.

Adekola *et al.* (2007) confirm that, forestry institutions across the country are concerned with education that provide the individual a general and broad based knowledge about forest and related resources which are mostly focus itself with the individual acquisition of new manipulative skills, technical knowledge, vocational skills and problem solving attitudes and abilities.

Teaching either theoretical or practical is a complex phenomenon which is grinding the learner through a variety of selected experiences to bring about worthwhile changes in behaviors. Teaching also connotes a lot of other meanings if used without verification; it could refer to a human action. Thus involves relationship based on interaction. It could be said to be a social function that aims at grinding desirable growth in others. Teaching or lecturing is a notable profession because it has the characteristics of other profession that is to say it is a means of livelihood, which is jealously graded by those who belong to it. Usually it sets standard for admission of new members and prescribed code of ethics for retention of its members. Like in other profession, either technologists or forestry lecturers all over the world have professional organization. Such as in Nigeria, International Professional Agriculturist of Nigeria (IPAN) Academic Union of Research Institute of Nigeria (ACURI), and so on. While in United State of America, it is called National Association of America Teachers. In Britain, it is National Union of Teachers.

Forestry education is the education which student receive after secondary education. The Nigerian’s philosophy of education believes that forestry

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ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

education is a very important instrument both for individual and national development and that forestry education should be geared towards providing a broad general knowledge on forestry education for tertiary school leavers in order to fit them into the society. These objectives are in line with the current National policy on Education (2004) which observes that the broad goal of education shall be to prepare the individual for useful living in the society. For these objective to be achieved, both lecturer and instructors should be highly motivated financially materially and morally to enhance high productivity. According to Lawretta (2009), financial reward or gain has direct benefit which reinforces the action of a teacher positively and plays a vital role in the determination of an employee's job morale and satisfaction. And, the success of any educational system depends to a large extent on the high productivity of the instructors or lecturers who operate the school as vehicles to achieve the educational objectives. He stated further that, Instructors/Lecturer constantly complains of job dissatisfaction which of course is probably the course of lack of commitment in their work and this situation adversely affects their performance on the job. And that the contemporary instructor/lecturers keep on complaining of poor salary, poor conditions of service and lack of status in the society. In this paper, a strategy to be adopted to motivate lecturer or instructors towards high productivity is examined.

Why Does Nigeria Need Forestry Education

The question of why Nigeria needs forestry education may appear too simplistic and unnecessary to the novies. Even the political conditions in Nigeria for the past thirty years leave no room for continuity. Over the year, political power in Nigeria has been used to entrench mediocrity, corruption in high places, misplace priority and conservative attitude of people. The direct effect of these is a battered economy and an educational system that decaying by the day. According to Adekola *et al.* (2007) note that forestry education and manpower development are the principal processes by which the transformation of the society is being progressively carried out. And, the 21st century forester has to be provided with skills for forest establishment, management skills of diver's nature, skills for decent environment, new skills in forest resources utilization for consumption skill in forest for the people's concept placing necessary values on the lives of resources and skills in the preservation of wild life.

Oguntala (1991) observes that shortage of skills manpower is one of the biggest obstacles faced by the developing countries in their effort to develop and exploit their forest resources. And the purpose of manpower development is to ensure the presence of right number of employee, with right skills in the right job at the right time and performing the right activities in order to achieve the objective of the organization. The objectives of forestry

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ISSN: 2141 - 4181

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education as contained in the National Policy of Education includes (i) the acquisition, development and inculcating of a proper value orientation for survival of individual and society. (ii) Development of intellectual capabilities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environment. (iii) The acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community, and (iv) The acquisition of objective views of local and external environment (Adekola *et al.*, 2007).

Akoru (1988), stated that the success of any educational system depends to a large extent on the high productivity of teachers who operate the schools as vehicles to achieve educational objectives. He concluded that lecturers/instructors constantly complain of job dissatisfaction which of course is probably the cause of lack of commitment in their work and this situation adversely affects their performance on the job. And, they keep on complaining of poor salary, poor condition of service and lack of station in the society.

This paper examined strategies to be adopted in order to motivate forestry lecturers/instructors toward high productivity in Nigeria.

General Rules and Theories of Motivation

One of the greatest challenges facing the educational system is how to effectively motivate forestry lecturers/instructors towards high productivity. According to Lawretta (2009), motivation means the reason why somebody does something in a particular way. It kicks like an engine, leading to action. The term motivation is derived from a Latin word 'movere' which means to move to action. And it is a something that affects behavior.

Motivation is a complex internal state of an individual, which we cannot observe directly, but indirectly, it affects behavior. It is an internal psychological process that is very difficult to see but one can observe its presence or absence as a person performing his or her tasks. For example, if lecturers or instructors are working willingly, the organization may think that they are motivated but when they are chatting with their colleagues when they supposed to work people may think they are not motivated. Therefore motivation is an internal psychological state of an individual or totality of those inner striving conditions such as wishes, desires and drives that make individual to act in particular way to achieve a purpose. Based on Okonkwo (1996) definition which says:

"In general terms of organizational behavior, motivation is the process by which management enable employees to direct their energies towards maximum attainment

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ISSN: 2141 - 4181

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of the goals and objective of the organization that is, toward a fulfillment of the desires of management at all the time”.

Okonkwo stresses further that, it is not only for willingness to do something but also the ability to satisfy some needs for the individuals. This is the reason why motivation is based on the needs of the people that is being provided at right time. And this is the reason that it is an intervening variable between human needs as described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Triangle of Motivation
Source: Okonkwo, (1996).

The Parameters between Motivation, Human Needs and Behavior

Motivation is the process of arousing movement into actions in the organism (Okoye, 2007). Many authors look at motivation in various ways. Motivation is a constant, never ending, fluctuating and complex and that it is an almost universal characteristics of particularly every organism state of affairs (Lawretta, 2009). It is a moving power that makes an individual to strive to achieve a set goal despite difficulties. Many experts from various fields have come with various theories of motivation. Some believe that if workers are given sufficient money regularly, they will be motivated and work efficiently and more effectively. Therefore, they call for the policy of more work, more pay in order to improve their productivity. Lawretta stated further that, the chief proponent of this theory is Fredrick Taylor which noted that human relation theorists believe that workers should be rewarded by the use of promotions and conducive working environment should be accorded to the workers. Also like the theory of Mc Gregory's of 'X' believes that fair pay should be given to work with good relationship and that workers needs should be met. Lawretta stated further that the five areas of needs are psychological needs, physical safety and security, needs for love, affection and belonging, needs for self and social esteem and self-actualization.

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ISSN: 2141 - 4181

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The under-listed figures are the five hierarchical order of Abraham Maslow, (1970) theory which can be simply modify into pyramid of needs or motivation. Figure 2 shows that the needs of the workers are to be looked into properly and help them to solve their needs immediately. Although human needs differ from one another and changes with situation and period of time.

Figure 2: Pyramid of Needs
Source: Abraham Maslow, (1970).

The Importance of Motivating Lecturer/Instructors

The relevant of lecturing/instructing as a profession cannot be over emphasized in our society. It is an asset to every society. The development of any society depends on the quality of the professional's output. Some educationist, philosophers and psychologist; defined teaching as an act of impacting knowledge, skill and wisdom to group of persons with a view of making them educated and it has to do with training or instructing a person for the general development of the society.

In fact, virtually all the sectors of Nigerian economy depend largely on the product of schools and teachers to succeed. The government is not left out in benefiting from teachers. All the public and private parastatals have to be set with quality personnel. Must have pass through one school or the other.

The technological advancement in the world nowadays prove that things are changing scientifically and rapidly to pave ways for new motivations and this prove that the responsibility of both lecturers and instructor is highly needed. Lawretta (2009) confirmed that there is no gainsaying the fact that teacher is a teacher whether at the primary, secondary or tertiary institution and that the inculcate knowledge to his/her students. In fact, they even occupy a vital role in any educational process and in the formation of human capital. According to a book published by Morphet, John and Reller 1974) in Lawretta (2009)

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“of all these several major plans which administrators must develop is as critical to the success of the undertaker as those affecting the people responsible for their implementation”

Ukaje (1983) conformed that teachers are the hub of any educational system and just as the wheel rotates round the hub, the educational system rotates around teachers. In fact, no educational system can be better than teacher.

Development and progress of both the school and society fall squarely on the teachers, due to poor motivation that measures their high productivity. The rates at which students fall in the school’s examination appear to indicate that the investment of the society’s scarce resources in educational system is wasted. The society must do everything in its power to motivate the staff or individuals within it to achieve excellence in terms of self-actualization which can be done by means of consciously planned inducement and incentives (Lawretta, 2012). Thus, the higher the level of satisfaction given to the lecturers or instructors, the higher the level of production and development in the society and even making them to work beyond their normal working period and output.

Strategies and prospect for motivation lecturers/instructors in Nigeria

Since teachers are very dynamic and full of potentials to be discovered, nurtured and properly motivated channeled as national investment toward producing better and more useful citizens. No school can function very well without teacher because they are the programme operators strategies been discovered to be very useful in improving teacher’s zeal for effectiveness and better improvement.

It is believed that the style and quality of leadership exhibited by the school Provost or Vice Chancellor appear to affect a teacher motivation and hence his productivity. Provost or vice chancellor should offer a challenging research work to lecturers or instructor and try to increase their degree of control over workers and also provide opportunity for participative decision making.

The key to a successful school is an effective instructor/lecturer and management. The management motivates the teacher; they become not only willing but also happy to do their jobs.

Factors Controlling Motivation and High Productivity

Promotion from time to time: This always led to lecturer and instructor’s high productivity because it improves working condition of the workers and reduction in grumbling and complaining for the realization of many tertiary schools. This appear to be the reason why Lawretta (2009) suggested that a re-

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ISSN: 2141 - 4181

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appraisal of teachers job satisfaction should be continuous and made a national issue to ensure that the right caliber of teaching staff are retained.

More so, one may rightly say that motivation does not come when there is increase in salaries and some teachers refuse to do their work or remain unsatisfied. In this case the situation could be attributed to personality traits such as laziness, apathy, health problem, family problem and so on. Other factors that contribute to high productivity are as follows. (i) Increase in salary and wages (ii) improve condition of service (iii) adequate provision of instructional materials and facilities (iv) quality of students (v) levels of knowledge understanding and experience of lecturer and instructors.

Conclusion

Without controversy, motivation is a key for high productivity of both lecturer and instructor. It is the duty of government and stakeholders to motivate the teachers from time to time so as to make them happy. As adage say "Happiness always leads to joy" but if not; they feign laziness and lead to incompetence of their duties.

Recommendation

Based on the forgoing strategies established for motivating lecturer and instructors should be motivated towards high productivities for the realization of tertiary education system and objectives. The following recommendation was suggested:

Government and all stakeholders should join hands together to improve the welfare package of the lecturers and instructors. Such as increment in salaries and wages, in service training, seminar, workshops and good conductive environment etc. Other incentive like cash awards certificate of outstanding performance in national and external competition or periodic test should be given to them at when due.

Finally, act of indiscipline should be eradicated to improve better performance of students' lecturer and instructor for better productivity.

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